

A Review of the Instructional Practices for Promoting Online Learning Communities

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An effective learning community helps foster positive student learning experiences and outcomes. However, in distance learning environments, the communication barriers inevitably hinder the interaction among the students because of the lower levels of social presence. These barriers present challenges in building learning communities in an online environment. In the past 20 years, distance education researchers and educators have studied and experimented with various instructional strategies and tools to reduce these barriers in order to facilitate students to form effective online learning communities. This systematic literature review examines the instructional strategies and tools that have been used to achieve the goal. The review results will be reported in terms of the essential elements of OLC building, types of instructional strategies and tools, and the instructional implications.

INTRODUCTION

Two decades after the internet became available, online instruction has become an important part in education. Besides the fully online courses, incorporating online components in regular face-to-face courses has also become the norm rather than a novelty today. In order to enhance students' learning experience and outcomes, online educators have tried to trans-

plant various face-to-face instructional methods, approaches, or strategies into this new learning environment. The online learning community is one of them. Online Learning Communities (OLC) have recently received increasing attention in the field of online education (Ke & Hoadley, 2009). A learning *community* helps promote positive learning experiences and better learning outcomes in distance learning environments (Stepich & Ertmer, 2003). However, one inevitable tradeoff in an online learning environment is a decrease in the quality of social interaction and the degree of social presence. Social interaction is naturally inherent in traditional face-to-face classrooms. Among the essential components of a community, interaction between the members is deemed to be one of the crucial factors that make a community alive. It is not only critical in helping the learners to develop a sense of belongingness within a learning community, but also determines the dynamics of the learning community.

Interaction within an online environment is mediated by the communication between the participants. The physical distance and communication barriers imposed by the media inevitably affect the psychological perception of the participants, and as a result, the degree of social presence of the participants is decreased. By definition, social presence is “the degree of awareness of another person in an interaction and the consequent appreciation of an interpersonal relationship” (Tu, 2002, p. 294). As the degree of social presence declines, the communication is perceived as more impersonal. The low social presence in online learning environments creates an invisible obstacle that undermines quality social interactions, and thus may hinder online learners’ development of a sense of a learning community.

In response to this issue, there has been a call for efforts to create a “human touch of attentiveness to their students” in distance learning (Regalbuto, et al., 1999, p. 2), and facilitate online learning experiences that more closely resemble traditionally accepted practices (Meyen, Tangen, & Lian, 1999). In the past two decades, researchers have been conceptualizing principles and models for facilitating effective OLC building (e.g. Community of Inquiry framework (CoI), Garrison, Anderson, & Archer, 2000), analyzing essential elements of OLC (e.g. Rovai, 2002; Shea, Swan, Li, & Pickett, 2005;), advising instructional design guidelines (e.g. Slagter van Tryon & Bishop, 2006) and instructional strategies (e.g. Macdonald & Poniatowska, 2011) for promoting students’ senses of OLC. Yet, what instructional guidelines and strategies have been implemented in promoting OLC in real settings? How effective are they? To gain a better understanding about OLC and how effective these strategies are for facilitating students to form their OLC and benefit from it, we conducted a literature review to examine this

very issue. In the following, we will first review the related literature to construct a conceptual framework of OLC. Then, using the conceptual framework as a guide, we will examine the instructional practices for enhancing OLC and their effectiveness.

METHODS

A systematic literature review was conducted to examine the current practice and formats in helping students form learning communities in on-line environments by promoting social interaction and social presence. Combinations of keywords (online, learning community, virtual learning community, learning community building, social interaction, social presence) were used in searching the literature from 1990-2012 in ERIC, PsychInfo, Academic Search Premier, E-Journals. The initial search resulted in 144 articles that either had the keywords in their titles or keyword list. The researchers further filtered the results and narrowed the list of inclusion down to 106 articles by examining the abstracts of the articles. The final step in the selection process was reviewing the content of the articles. In this final selection process, the list of the article was narrowed down to 45 articles to be included in the review based on the criteria that (1) the instruction was completely online or hybrid, (2) the main goal of the study was to promote OLC, (3) the instructional strategies utilized were to enhance social interaction or presence in the OLC. The researchers also developed a conceptual framework for examining the effects of the instructional strategies utilized in these studies in enhancing social presence and interaction in light of promoting OLC. This conceptual framework consists of four components: theoretical conception, interaction, social presence, and tools. In the following, we will discuss this framework in detail.

ONLINE LEARNING COMMUNITIES (OLC)

Researchers have attempted to define what an online learning community is since online learning has become an important component in education. Some definitions are simple but cover a broad spectrum of types of OLC, for example, “a bounded group of students involved in cooperative learning online” (Misanchuk & Anderson, 2001, p. 3); while some are more elaborate and therefore more descriptive, such as, “for a virtual learning community to exist, it is necessary for individuals to take advantage of, and

in some cases invent, a process for engaging ideas, negotiating meaning and learning collectively” (Schwier, 2007, p. 69). Thus, online learning communities could be seen as communities that are established in a virtual environment to achieve the goal of enhancing learning processes, experiences, and outcomes. However, though these definitions may give us an idea of what an online learning community is and how it may look, they do not provide a clear picture of what exactly constitutes an effective OLC. In the following, we will start our conceptualization of OLC by identifying the essential components of community and learning community. Then, we will examine how these elements of a learning community are affected when the environment where it resides and operates is changed from a physical setting to an online setting.

Community

What is a community? Using Bohm dialogue, Guilar and Loring (2008) dissected the word and identified *common*, *communal*, and *communication* as its semantic roots. By this semantic analysis, a community can be considered a group of members who gather together in order to accomplish a shared common goal or interest (root of common), by mutually contributing and receiving substance/effort to or from other members (root of communal), through constant interaction (root of communication). These three basic roots work together to bond the members together to form a functional community. First of all, most researchers agree (e.g. Duncan-Howell, 2010; Rovai, 2002; Shea, Swan, Li, & Pickett, 2005) that the shared common goal or interest is the first ingredient that triggers the creation of a community, as well as the first component of a community. Without a common interest or goal that requires more than one person to accomplish it, there is no motivation for members to gather as a group. Secondly, one of the main reasons for an individual to join a group is to take advantage of other members’ contribution in order to enable him or her to accomplish his/her own goal. However, the community will not continue if the sharing or contribution among members is unidirectional, rather than bi-directional or multi-directional. This communal nature manifests itself as the second component of community, which is interdependency (Rovai, 2002). This interdependency is an essential component in sustaining the continuity of a community. Next, the interdependency among a group of people naturally links to the third root of a community, which is communication. Communication is the mechanism that changes interdependency into a reality. When there is communication,

there is interaction. Therefore, interaction logically becomes the third component of a community (Rovai, 2002; Russell & Ginsberg, 1999). Interaction is a process of verbal information and/or physical actions exchange that occur naturally within a group of people when there is a need for them to communicate. During interaction, group members exchange information (verbal, physical, psychological, or emotional) through their behaviors. Thus, interaction can also be seen as the behavioral component of a community that is necessary to realize the interdependency component of a community.

The common goal, interdependency, and interaction are the three main components of a community and reciprocally influence each other. The common goal component not only functions as an initiator for the formation of a community, but also serves as the overall purpose of the community. It initiates the gathering of members and creates the need for interdependency among the members. Furthermore, interdependency necessitates interaction among the members for accomplishing the shared goal. However, though there is a shared common goal among the members, each individual member plays different roles, serves different functions, and assumes different responsibilities in order to maintain the operation of the community. Naturally, when humans interact, a social dimension emerges. Therefore, in addition to the individual psychological and behavioral variables, a number of social variables arise from the interdependency and interaction. These variables reciprocally intertwine and shape the nature and quality of the interdependency and interaction component. Relationship, support, trust, and history are four variables that most pertain to our topic.

Relationship. When two people interact, a relationship forms. A relationship connects two or more people in a certain way because it defines the nature of the interaction between or among people, and in turn, dictates the behaviors of each individual during the interaction. For an individual to identify him or herself as a member of a community and be willing to actively participate in the activities, he or she needs to feel the connectedness (Rovai, 2002; Shea, Swan, Li, & Pickett, 2005) and a sense of belonging (Duncan-Howell, 2010; Vratulis & Dobson, 2008). As a result, a sense of membership is developed (Rovai, 2002). These senses of connectedness, belongingness, and membership are formed through building various types of relationships with other members in the community. These variables are the key psychosocial variables that determine the degree of an individual sense of community (Rovai, 2002; Shea, Swan, Li, & Pickett, 2005).

Support. As mentioned above, a community is formed for a purpose, rather than a random gathering of people. With a shared goal or common

interest, the members interdepend on each other to accomplish the goal or realize their interest by receiving other members' help. This interdependency is operationalized as support from members in order to maintain the operation of the community and collectively move forward to the goal. This support could be physical, psychological, emotional, social, intellectual, or simply informational. The nature of support depends upon the goal of the community as well as the type of the relationships between the members. As Duncan-Howell (2010) contended, social or psychological support in a community is important for stabilizing a community. A community cannot exist without support from its members. It is a critical element for the success of reaching the goal for the community because it is what connects all the members together as a whole.

Trust. Trust is a critical socio-psychological variable in the formation as well as the health of a community (Liu, Magjuka, Bonk, & Lee, 2007). This variable does not have a direct effect on the common shared goal component of a community. However, it affects the interdependency and interaction components in an implicit way. When trust is absent, the relationships between and among the members become fragile. Fragile relationships could undermine the quality of interdependency and push it toward a negative direction, which decreases the degree of interdependency. When interdependency decreases, interaction decreases. When these two components of a community go into a negative direction, a likely result is that the community becomes dysfunctional, the goal of the community will not be accomplished, and the community may eventually collapse. Therefore, though trust is an implicit variable and usually stays in the background, it is a crucial variable that cannot be neglected when maintaining a community and facilitating its growth.

History. History is probably a variable likely to be overlooked in the concept of community. A community is almost never formed instantaneously. The formation of a community is a gradual process. Researchers have observed this phenomenon and suggested there are different stages or levels in a community development. For example, from a relationship development perspective, Brown (2001) described three stages of community development as making acquaintance, community conferment, and camaraderie. Rovai (2002) echoed the Brown's view of community development and deemed overlapping history among members as one of the essential elements of a community. A community defines itself with its development and growth overtime. This collective history of a community is a result of the interactions among its members. This history variable of a community was examined by Yeh (2010), who observed and analyzed the process of com-

munity formation. Yeh (2010) concluded that motivation and acquaintance, socialization and belongingness, information exchange and consensus, tacit understanding and development occur as the community progresses from its first formation to its maturity.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of OLC.

Learning Community

Putting the conceptual framework of community into the context of learning (see Figure 1), the concept of learning community may then be described as a group of individuals gathered together to (1) achieve a shared common goal, which is learning a given subject; (2) interdepend on each other for enhancing learning experience, broadening perspectives, or making learning more effective and efficient; and (3) interact with other members who assume various roles and possess various competency at various degrees in order to achieve their own learning goal. Thus, the goal and purpose of learning a subject define the nature of the interdependency in a learning community, as well as its psycho-social contextual elements (e.g. peer-to-peer relationships, student-instructor relationship, facilitation and guidance support from the instructor, support of related knowledge and multiple perspectives from the peers). Furthermore, the common goal also defines the types of interaction within a community. In the case of learning

community, three modes of interaction, as described by Anderson and Garrison (1998), are student-student, student-teacher, and student-content.

Student-student interaction. Clearly, a community is a social environment where all types of interactions occur for achieving the common goal. In this social environment, the sense of community, connectedness, and membership are the key psychological constructs that fulfill the interdependency component in a community. In the case of a learning community, these three constructs are largely engendered from student-student interaction. The quality of student-student interaction has a direct impact on the development of relationship, trust, and support elements of a learning community. Anderson and Garrison (1998) contend that support is especially critical in a learning community because it is a reinforcer for students' intellectual growth. Vygotsky's (1978) social constructivist theory has clearly pointed out that learning is a social activity and cannot be separated from its social context. His theory of zone of proximal development (ZPD) (Vygotsky, 1978) also provides a conceptual ground for the necessity of student-student interaction in a learning community where students with higher competence could provide support to students with lower competence. In return, by having to explain the concepts to their peers, highly competent students deepen their understanding of the subject. Through this interaction, the common goal of learning the subject is achieved.

Student-teacher interaction. Teaching and learning are two sides of a coin. In either face-to-face or online learning environments, in order for effective and deep learning to occur, interaction between students and teacher is essential. As Anderson and Garrison (1998) described, the instructor guides students' learning by introducing and explaining the concepts under study, and then students ask questions for clarification of the concepts, performing the skills just learned for instructor feedback. With students' performance and questions, the instructor can help students correct their misunderstandings as well as improve their performance. Thus, the constant flow of information exchange between students and teacher will result in a positive interaction, which is a key for the teacher to provide support to students, foster trust, and strengthen the relationship.

Student-content interaction. Anderson and Garrison (1998) also suggested that a mode of interaction occurs between student and content. The interaction between student and content is the cognitive process in learning, in which they receive the information about the content, comprehend it, elaborate on it with their prior knowledge, and apply it in solving problems or completing some tasks (Anderson, 1995; Farr, 1987; Stillings, 1995). This interaction has a direct connection with the component of common

goal in a learning community. In this case, the subject to be studied provides the context for not only the student-content interaction, but also student-teacher and student-student interactions. An explicit context helps put these two modes of interaction in perspective, and in turn, enhances and enriches students' understanding about the subject and the application of the knowledge.

Learning Community in Online Environments

As discussed in the beginning of the paper, an online learning community (OLC) is a learning community that is formed in virtual environments. It shares all the major components and psychological, social elements with a typical learning community in traditional face-to-face educational settings. The most distinctive difference between traditional face-to-face learning communities and online learning communities is the form of communication. The members in traditional learning communities interact through direct face-to-face communication, while members of OLC interact through various types of mediated communication, for example, text, audio, or video transmission. During the process of communication, according to Shannon and Weaver's model of communication (1949), part of the information is unavoidably lost or delayed in the transmission because of the fidelity affordance of the medium (or media). Some media afford higher fidelity of information than others, for example, video versus text. Human interaction is mainly realized by exchanging information between the sender and receiver. Thus, the medium's affordability of information fidelity would inevitably affect the quality of interaction. Affordability of information in a medium determines the amount and quality of verbal as well as socio-psychological information exchanged during communication. The fidelity affordability of verbal information determines the quality of intellectual communication. The fidelity of affordability of social-psychological information could affect the quality of social-psychological elements of a learning community. The social-psychological information could include the sender's facial expression, body language, gestures, tone of voice, and others. The degree of this information that the receiver is able to perceive is likely to affect the receiver's perception about the signaler being "real." This phenomenon has been termed by Short, Williams, and Christie (1976) as *social presence*. The low social presence in online learning environments has been identified as one of the main factors that accounts for students' dissatisfaction with online learning (Gunawardena & Zittle, 1997). Social presence also has a di-

rect impact on the building of an effective OLC because of its critical role in communication, which consequently determines the quality of interaction within the OLC.

Social presence

According to Short, Williams, and Christie (1976), social presence can be defined as “the degree of salience of the other person in a mediated interaction and the consequent salience of the interpersonal interaction” (p. 65). In describing how humans process information received from external sources, Paivio (1971, 1986) explained it with his dual coding theory. He contended that the human cognitive system is comprised of dual symbolic subsystems: verbal and nonverbal. Information and knowledge are processed and represented in verbal, nonverbal, or dual formats. During the encoding process, the nonverbal system processes and represents information about nonverbal objects and events (including visual, auditory, haptic and other modalities), while the verbal system handles verbal information.

With the explanation of Paivio’s dual coding theory, it is clear why and how social presence suffers in technology-mediated communication environments. According to Argyle and Dean (1965) and Wiener and Mehrabian (1968), the two components of social presence are *intimacy* and *immediacy*. Intimacy refers to physical proximity, visual cues (such as eye contact, body language) and topic of communication (during the information exchange). Immediacy regards the psychological distance that is set by the signaler to the receiver in an event of communication. It has also been referred to as “e-mmediacy” by Slagter van Tryon and Bishop (2006, p. 52) specifically for communication in online learning environments. The degrees of intimacy and immediacy affect learners’ perceptions of other learners’ presence (“being a real person” and “being there” Kehrwald, 2008, p. 95) in OLC. Though social presence is typically reduced or limited significantly in online learning environments, it is not necessarily true in all cases. Kehrwald (2008) suggested that degree of social presence varies with the various affordability of the online learning environment. It may be seen as a function of the level of affordability of communication modality (text, audio, or video) utilized, the instructional delivery mode (synchronous or asynchronous), and the employment of instructional strategies (e.g. group work for increasing the frequency of communication among learners, or real-time conversations for increasing the degree of immediacy).

Therefore, though OLC has its inherent barriers that tend to reduce social presence during the interaction among the learners and the instructor,

these barriers are possible to be overcome with various instructional delivery modes, approaches, strategies, and tools. In the following, we will examine what has been used in enhancing students' sense of OLC by addressing the components of OLC and their associated elements or constructs discussed thus far.

INSTRUCTIONAL INTERVENTIONS FOR ENHANCING OLC

Since the beginning of online education, a sense of isolation among online students has been an important issue and research topic for online education researchers and educators. Over the past two decades, a number of instructional approaches, strategies, and tools have been implemented in a hope to alleviate the communication barriers inherent in online environments and in turn promote students' learning experience, sense of learning community, and ultimately learning outcomes. What approaches and strategies have been implemented? How well are they aligned with the theoretical principles and guidelines? How effective are they? In the following, we will report our findings by the components (interaction, interdependency, common goal, and history) identified in the conceptual framework of OLC discussed earlier.

Interaction

Our review showed that the majority of the instructional approaches and strategies for promoting a student's sense of OLC and satisfaction of online learning experience were targeted at addressing various types or aspects of the interaction component. Based on the conceptual framework of OLC discussed above, this result indicated that the educators' efforts in promoting OLC have been conceptually sound and on target. As mentioned earlier, there are three types of interaction and they are different in the nature of the interaction because of the type of the relationships (i.e. student-student, student-instructor, & student-content). Therefore, the instructional approaches and strategies are different for facilitating each type of interaction.

Student-student interaction. The instructional approach and strategies for enhancing this type of interaction mainly deal with the psychological construct of social presence. The majority of these instructional interventions reported in the literature fell into this category. First of all, to over-

come the intimacy barriers in online environments, audio conferencing (Anderson & Garrison, 1995) and video conferencing (Latchem, 1995) have been reported to have the necessary capacity to increase social presence. Also, in a six-credit hour doctoral Leadership course in which forty students enrolled, Woods and Keeler (2001) used audio emails to decrease the physical distance and promote students' senses of OLC. These tools reduce the communication barrier caused by the physical distance between the students with providing high fidelity affordability channels (audio and video) for the psychological information to be more easily and naturally transmitted from the signaler to the receiver. Also, online real time chats have as well been used to enhance the students' interaction for this purpose as well (Tsai, Laffey, & Hanuscin, 2010).

In terms of addressing the immediacy issue, a collaborative learning approach was the most common instructional practice for promoting student-student interaction. In this review, we found that a number of variations of collaborative learning approaches have been implemented for this purpose, such as various types of group work that required students to work together toward a shared goal (Guilar & Loring, 2008; Kanuka, 2011; Hiltz, 1998; Liu, Magjuka, Bonk, & Lee, 2007). Other more specific examples include cooperative learning that requires more structure in term of students' roles and responsibility (Yeh, 2010), collaborative problem-based learning (PBL) (Guilar & Loring, 2008; Hann, Glowacki-Dudka & Conceicao-Runlee, 2000; Yeh, 2010), or collaborative constructivist learning (Bélanger, 2008; Lee, Carter-Wells, Glaeser, Ivers, & Street, 2006). Though a collaborative learning approach is very effective in creating a learning environment where student-student interaction is likely to be higher, simply putting students in a collaborative learning format sporadically may not foster a strong and stable sense of learning community among them. In studying 67 undergraduate teacher education students in an Application of Instructional Technology course, Overbaugh and Lin (2006) concluded that continuity and cumulateness are two keys for continuously generating adequate interaction among the students in order to promote social presence.

Furthermore, social strategies are another frequently used instructional strategy category for enhancing the immediacy of student-student interaction. These strategies included social tasks, for example, self-introduction (Kerr, 2009); making oneself known, developing an explicit identity within the group, getting to know others (Cameron, Morgan, Williams, & Kostecky, 2009); providing social space for the students to engage in social tasks (e.g. Facebook or MySpace, Kerr, 2009; Rosson, et al, 2009); or debates (Kanuka, 2011). Also, Dawson (2010) took a very different ap-

proach using social network analysis (SNA) to visually represent the interaction among the students by diagramming their networking status with their peers and instructors. By monitoring 1026 students' networking with peers in a chemistry unit in a length of one semester at a university that had approximately 42,000 students, this tool provided early warnings for an instructor to identify troubled or inadequate interactions among the students and therefore could respond with timely facilitation as needed.

Other types of social strategies include a peer mentor approach, such as spontaneous facilitation in independent group work (Wang & Chen, 2010), participatory design where learning activities were designed with the aim of promoting interaction (Rosson, et al., 2009), and peer-assisted OLC (Ruan & Lin, 2007). The effects of these social strategies were generally positive. However, providing explicit structure of the instruction and activities, such as setting ground rules (Wang & Chen, 2010) or setting participation expectations (Kerr, 2009), is the key for these strategies to be successful.

Online discussions are the most common instructional activity used in online instructional environments for substituting in-class discussion in traditional face-to-face classrooms. Most of the online discussions are not necessarily used for enhancing students' senses of OLC, but it could afford such function by increasing social presence (or immediacy). This is achieved by using the discussion board for students to share professionally relevant information and provide emotional or psychological support (Hramiak, 2010). One particular effective strategy that Du, Havard, and Li (2005) used was dynamic discussion, which was based on a framework proposed by Oliver and McLoughlin (1996, cited in Du et al, 2005). The framework consists of five types of interactions (social, procedural, expository, explanatory, and cognitive) in three general processes (information, methods, and cognition). Based on this framework, they designed and implemented a dynamic discussion in a graduate course for two semesters. During the dynamic discussion, the students were required to provide support and assist other students when they struggled with course requirements. The students reviewed other students' responses to the discussion or provided suggestions to other students' requests for help, and in turn, they were appreciated by the students they helped. This approach created a learning environment where support was expected and reciprocal, and therefore, enhanced the students' sense of OLC. However, they also found that simple guidance provided in the discussion sessions would not necessarily promote students building of OLC. Again, explicit guidance and structure in directing and requiring students' engagement in the discussion is needed for the effects to occur.

Student-teacher interaction. The tools and instructional practices for enhancing the intimacy in student-teacher interaction are identical to student-student interaction, therefore, we will not repeat them here. In this section, we will focus our discussion on the instructional strategies used to enhance interaction between students and instructor for the purpose of promoting students' sense of OLC and learning experience. In OLC, Garrison, et al. (2000) further distinguish the types of presence into social presence, teaching presence, and cognitive presence, depending upon the parties involved in the interaction. Social presence mainly occurs in the student-student interaction due to its social nature. Therefore, the immediacy in student-instructor interaction is largely reflected in teaching presence. In their case study of the perception of graduate students from 27 online MBA courses, Liu, Magjuka, Bonk, and Lee (2007) found that instructors regularly posting announcements and providing feedback had a significant correlation relationship with the students' sense of OLC. Another channel for an instructor to make a stronger teaching presence is to create explicit structure for the class and incorporate activities, assignments, or projects that encourage all three types of interaction (Jones, 2011). Zydney, deNoyelles, Seo (2012) compared two fully online classes of graduate students' interactions in an asynchronous online discussion on their readings about Spiro and others' Cognitive Flexibility Theory. One group used "Save the Last Word for Me" protocol, while the control group used a regular asynchronous discussion format. The results showed that using this protocol to structure students' participation in online discussion increased the quality of social, cognitive, and teaching presence. It also elevated their ownership of postings, which could have promoted their sense of membership and connectedness to the OLC.

Though contemporary instructional theories emphasize the need to encourage students' development of self-directed and independent study skills, teaching presence is still a key to an efficient learning process, and sometimes, makes collaboration and interaction among students happen. As Overbaugh and Lin (2006) observed, the effects of teaching presence was more prominent and necessary in online learning environments than face-to-face classrooms in facilitating students' interaction and learning process. However, a caution was given by Vonderwell, Xin & Alderman's (2007) from their case study on exercising teaching presence in OLC. By examining the data from five master's level of online courses over three semesters (courses including *educational research, planning for technology*, and multiple sessions of *technology in the classroom*), they concluded that the instructor should find an appropriate degree of teaching presence to balance

between keeping students engaged in the interaction process and over-interfering in student-student interaction because of its authoritative nature and the imbalance of power. Facilitating and encouraging student-to-student interaction in the background may be a good rule when considering choosing to employ teaching presence instructional strategies in OLC.

Student-content interaction. This type of interaction mainly involves students' cognitive processes and effort in understanding and elaborating on the domain specific concepts, information, and skills under study. Therefore, it is mostly reflected as cognitive presence. In order to enhance students' cognitive presence during the learning process in OLC environments, community of practice (CoP) (Lave & Wenger, 1991) as well as community of inquiry (CoI) (Garrison, Anderson, & Archer, 2000) have been implemented as instructional approaches to engage students in such interaction. Tsai, Laffey and Hanuscin (2010) used NETWORK (Nurturing Elementary Teachers' work) as a virtual communication platform to create a community of practice environment for teachers to exchange experiences and ideas for learning to teach. Also, CoP has been used in enhancing faculty who primarily teach online to make psychological connections to the institution and engage in faculty development (Velez, 2009). Similarly, a positive effect has also been found in utilizing community of inquiry to enhance learners' cognitive presence by contextualizing learning in relevant domain context (Kanuka, 2011).

Interdependency

As the conceptual framework of OLC indicates, relationship, support, and trust are three prominent social-psychological variables in relation to the component of interdependency. These three variables are typically perceived by students in an OLC as connectedness, sense of belonging, or membership. These social-psychological variables are largely hindered by the low degree of immediacy in communication interaction. In addressing this barrier, Waddill (2006) used action learning as an instructional strategy to encourage interaction among the management-level graduate students in a leadership program by requiring students to actively seek support from their peers and in turn, elevated the social-psychological variables. In this study, each student presented a real life problem of their own and called for help from the other students for solutions. However, though the idea was conceptually plausible, the effects of action learning were not noticeable and the sense of OLC was not built because offering help for finding the

solutions was volunteered in this study. Another approach being utilized was dialogic conversation in a hybrid program that has online as well as on-campus portions of curriculum (Guilar & Loring, 2008). Through dialogs and sharing personal thoughts during face-to-face meetings, the learners gradually develop relationships, trust, and a sense of caring and willingness to support their peers. By which, the group grew into a close-knit cohort and a sense of learning community (LC) was formed. This strong sense of LC was maintained and carried over into OLC during their online portion of curriculum. This hybrid format and LC-OLC sense building process was successful and could be a model for programs that have both on-campus and online components in their curricula. Furthermore, photovoice was another technique used to enhance the students' connectedness to the OLC (Perry, Dalton, & Edwards, 2009). Photovoice was used in this study as a teaching technology as well as a tool to elicit personal and interpersonal connections in the discussion. Fifteen graduate students in a change management course started their online discussion by first viewing a series of carefully selected photos. The students were required to interpret them with their own experiences and perspectives. This was to make the students' responses in the discussion more personal, and therefore, elevated the connectedness, sense of belonging, and trust. Lastly, in studying the key factors for developing and sustaining a learning community in an online environment, Kerr (2009) surveyed and interviewed distance learning teachers and students from 7th through 10th grades. She observed that encouraging students to develop a sense of ownership of their work played an important role in helping them establish their sense of membership in the OLC. Zydney, deNoyelles, and Seo's (2012) study echoed this observation.

Common goal

The common goal component is the purpose as well as the drive for the formation of an OLC. In an OLC, the shared goal also provides the context for the application of the knowledge and skills under study. Therefore, in addressing the issue of immediacy, instructional approaches that direct or require students to work together in order to complete some tasks that would lead to better learning outcomes could help them develop a sense of OLC. A number of instructional approaches have been used to facilitate students' building of OLC by taking advantage of this basic component in the instruction. They included collaborative learning approach (Hiltz, 1998; Bélanger, 2008), problem-based learning (PBL) (Yeh, 2010; Hann, Glowacki-

Dudka & Conceicao-Runlee, 2000), or group work (Liu, Magjuka, Bonk & Lee, 2007). Also, community of inquiry (CoI) is also an instructional approach that could afford similar effects (Akyol & Garrison, 2011; Zydney, deNoyelles, & Seo, 2012).

Moreover, the intimacy issue under the common goal component may be alleviated with providing opportunities for students to engage in activities that reduce the distance between subject matter and the real world applications (tangible applications). In light of this issue, both Kerr (2009) and Guilar & Loring (2008) found that the activities that were contextually meaningful and relevant to the common goal were necessary in order to attract learners to join and commit to the OLC. Community of practice is also an effective instructional approach for this purpose (Tsai, Laffey, & Hanuscin, 2010).

History

History is a component in OLC that tends to be overlooked. As discussed in the conceptual framework of OLC, the formation of an OLC is not instantaneous. It takes time to form and develop. The history is part of the identity of a community as well as its members. Therefore, being aware of and being part of creating the history of the OLC could help learners develop a strong sense of membership. Eksisozluk (Soylu, 2009) was a Turkish online dictionary website and collaborative learning community where the members reciprocally contributed and learned from other members' input to the refinement and repertoire of the vocabulary, and hence, an OLC in an informal learning setting. Two unique features on the website were the availability of the history of the OLC and individual identities that evolved through participation, which helped the learners identify themselves as members of the OLC. In educational settings, Guilar & Loring (2008) suggested that using a strong cohort model where the learners share the same history of their OLC could strengthen their commitment, sense of belonging, connectedness, as well as membership. One issue that may deserve attention from the research field of OLC is that online courses normally last one semester. Also, as discussed earlier, there are stages in the development of OLC. How to help students establish their OLC quickly and continuously maintain a high level of interaction and interdependency throughout the course will be an important research topic. The review results discussed in this section is also summarized in Table 1.

Table 1
Instructional approaches and strategies for enhancing OLC

Component of OLC	Element/type	Psychological construct	Instruction strategy/tools used to address		Implications
			Intimacy	Immediacy	
Common goal (context)			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Community of practice Meaningful activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaborative learning Community of inquiry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explicitly contextualizing and linking learning content to real life practice Creating an environment where some degrees of collaboration is required for effective learning
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relationship Support Trust 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connectedness Sense of belonging Membership 	N/A
Interdependency					

Table 1 continued

Component of OLC	Element/type	Psychological construct	Instruction strategy/tools used to address		Implications
			Intimacy	Immediacy	
Interaction	Student-student	Social presence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chats • Audio emails • Audio conferencing • Video conferencing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaborative learning • Social strategies • Discussions • Debates • Participatory design • Social space • Social/collaborative tools (Facebook, MySpace, blogs, wikis, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing multiple real time communication channels to promote level of intimacy • Embedding learning activities that require students to interact and in turn, build relationships and develop interdependency • Providing space and opportunities for social interaction outside of class time. • Explicit and clear structure and guidance for the activities
	Student-instructor	Teaching presence		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frequent announcements • Timely feedback • Explicit class structure • provide clear guidance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appropriate frequency presence through various formats (announcements, emails, comments during discussions, etc.) • Avoid being inactive for long period of time • Providing clear structure and rules for activities • Enforcing the rules • Allow flexibility for independent and creative thinking
History	Student-content	Cognitive presence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community of practice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community of inquiry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encouraging exploring the content domain • Providing guidance for developing scientific inquiry skills • Providing opportunities for solving real life subject related problems • Connecting students to real life community of practice
				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cohort model • Provision of OLC history 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Helping students identify themselves as part of the history of the OLC • Creating a cohort atmosphere within a class when cohort model is not possible

CONCLUSION

A learning community is a vital component in fostering a rich learning experience. The support that the peers and the instructors provide in a learning community is not only intellectual, but also social, psychological, and sometimes emotional. Building learning communities in online environments presents challenges because of the inherent obstacles that tend to decrease social presence and interactions of the students. In this review, we examined the existing literature in the field and conceptualized a framework that depicted the essential components and their elements of an OLC. Using this framework as a conceptual guide, we reviewed related literature pertaining to the instructional practices that were specifically aimed at promoting students' sense of OLC. We found that online education has been an innovative and dynamic field where the educators and researchers have been actively implementing and experimenting with different instructional tools, such as audio/video conferencing, to improve the quality of interaction by promoting the intimacy level. Also, a great number of instructional approaches and strategies have been used (e.g. collaborative learning, community of inquiry, photovoice, face-to-face LC transit to online OLC) to help the students develop necessary psychological connections with their peers and instructors. The instructional practices that we examined in this paper were generally effective for the purposes for which they were utilized, and the students' experiences were also positive. However, we found a pattern from the reports of this literature. That is, an explicit structure on the instructional activities designed to promote students' sense of OLC and clear rules for proceeding with the tasks in these activities are the key to make these instructional interventions effective. A high level of teaching presence could help elevate students' engagement (or their willingness) in the instructional activities. However, with another instructional goal of helping students become independent learners, the balance between giving clear structure for what the students should do and the space for them to develop their own intellectual gain and domain knowledge and psychological connections to the learning community is a difficult line to draw. More research effort is needed in elucidating the effectiveness of these instructional practices and tools on promoting OLC.

References

- Akyol, Z., & Garrison, D. R. (2011). Understanding cognitive presence in an online and blended community of inquiry: Assessing outcomes and processes for deep approaches to learning. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 42(2), 233-250.

- Anderson, J. R. (1995). *Learning and memory: An integrated approach*. New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- Anderson, T., & Garrison, R. (1995). Transactional Issues in distance education: The impact of design in audio conferencing. *American Journal of Distance Education, 9*(2), 27-45.
- Anderson, T., & Garrison, D.R. (1998). Learning in a networked world: New roles and responsibilities. In C. Gibson (Ed.), *Distance Learners in Higher Education*. (p. 97-112). Madison, WI: Atwood Publishing.
- Argyle, M., & Dean, J. (1965). Eye contact, distance, and affiliation. *Sociometry, 28*(3), 289-304.
- Bélanger, M. (2008). Online collaborative learning for labor education. *Labor Studies Journal, 33*(4), 412-430.
- Brown, R. (2001). The Process of Community-Building in Distance Learning Classes. *Journal of Asynchronous Learning Networks 5*(2).
- Cameron, B. A., Morgan, K., Williams, K. C., & Kostecky, K. L. (2009). Group projects: Student perceptions of the relationship between social tasks and a sense of community in online group work. *American Journal of Distance Education, 23*(1), 20-33.
- Dawson, S. (2010). 'Seeing' the learning community: An exploration of the development of a resource for monitoring online student networking. *British Journal of Educational Technology, 41*(5), 736-752.
- Du, Havard & Li (2005). Dynamic online discussion: Task-oriented interaction for deep learning. *Educational Media International, 42*(3), 207-218.
- Duncan-Howell, J. (2010). Teachers making connections: Online communities as a source of professional learning. *British Journal of Educational Technology, 41*(2), 324-340.
- Farr, M. J. (1987). *The long-term retention of knowledge and skills: A cognitive and instructional perspective*. New York: Springer-Verlag.
- Garrison, D. R., Anderson, T., Archer, W. (2000). Critical Inquiry in a text-based environment: computer conferencing in higher education. *The Internet and Higher Education, 2*(2-3), 87-105.
- Guilar, J. D., & Loring, A. (2008). Dialogue and Community in Online Learning: Lessons from Royal Roads University. *Journal of Distance Education, 22*(3), 19-40.
- Gunawardena, C. N., & Zittle, F. J. (1997). Social presence as a predictor of satisfaction with a computer - mediated conferencing environment. *American Journal of Distance Education, 11*, 8-26.
- Hann, D., Glowacki-Dudka, M., & Conceicao-Runlee, S. (2000). *147 practical tips for teaching online groups: Essentials of web-based education*. WI: Atwood Publishing.
- Hiltz, S. R. (1998). Collaborative Learning in Asynchronous Learning Networks: Building Learning Communities. In WebNet 98 World Conference of the WWW, Internet, and Intranet Proceedings (3rd, Orlando, FL, November 7-12). ERIC Document (ED 427705)
- Hramiak, A. (2010). Online learning community development with teachers as a means of enhancing initial teacher training. *Technology, Pedagogy and Education, 19*(1), 47-62.

- Jones, I. M. (2011). Can you see me now: Defining teaching presence in the online classroom through building a learning community. *Journal of Legal Studies Education*, 28(1), 67-116.
- Kanuka, H. (2011). Interaction and the online distance classroom: Do instructional methods effect the quality of interaction. *Journal of Computing in Higher Education*, 23(2-3), 143-156.
- Ke, F., & Hoadley, C. (2009). Evaluating online learning communities. *Educational Technology Research & Development*, 57, 487-510.
- Kehrwald, B. (2008). Understanding social presence in text-based online learning environments. *Distance Education*, 29(1), 89-106.
- Kerr, C. (2009). Creating Asynchronous Online Learning Communities. *Ontario Action Researcher*, 10(2), 1-20.
- Latchem, C. (1995). See what I mean? Where compressed digital video conferencing works. In F. Lockwood (Ed.), *Open and distance learning today* (pp. 98-107). London: Routledge.
- Lave, J., & Wenger, E. (1991). *Situated learning: Legitimate peripheral participation*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Lee, J., Carter-Wells, J., Glaeser, B., Ivers, K., & Street, C. (2006). Facilitating the development of a learning community in an online graduate program. *The Quarterly Review of Distance Education*, 7(1), 13-33.
- Liu, X., Magjuka, R. J., Bonk, C. J. & Lee, S.-H. (2007). Does sense of community matter: An examination of participants' perceptions of building learning communities in online courses. *Quarterly Review of Distance Education*, 8(1), 9-24.
- Macdonald, J., & Poniatowska, B. (2011). Designing the professional development of staff for teaching online: An OU (UK) case study. *Distance Education*, 32(1), 119-134.
- Meyen, E. Tangen, P., & Lian, C. (1999). Developing online instruction: Partnership between instructor and technical developers. *Journal of Special Education Technology*, 14(1), 18-31.
- Misanchuk, M., & Anderson, T. (2001). Building community in an online learning environment: Communication, cooperation and collaboration. Paper presented at the Mid-South Instructional Technology Conference, Murfreesboro, TN. Retrieved November 20, 2004, from <http://www.mtsu.edu/~itconf/proceed01/19.html>
- Murdock, J. L., & Williams, A. M. (2011). Creating an online learning community: Is it possible? *Innovative Higher Education*, 36, 305-315.
- Overbaugh, R. C., & Lin, S. Y. (2006). Student characteristics, sense of community, and cognitive achievement in web-based and lab-based learning environments. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 39(2), 205-223.
- Paivio, A. (1971). *Imagery and verbal processes*. New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston.
- Paivio, A. (1986). *Mental representations: A dual coding approach*. New York: Oxford University Press.

- Perry, B., Dalton, J., & Edwards, M. (2009). Photographic images as an interactive online teaching technology: Creating online communities. *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*, 20(2), 106-115.
- Perry, B., & Edwards, M. (2010). Creating a culture of community in the online classroom using artistic pedagogical technologies. In G. Veletsianos (Ed.), *Emerging technologies in distance education*. Canada: Athabasca University.
- Regalbutto, J., et al. (1999). *Teaching at an internet distance: The pedagogy of online teaching and learning*. The Report of a 1998- 1999 University of Illinois Faculty Seminar, December 7, 1999.
- Rosson, M. B., Sinha, H., Zhao, D., Carroll, J., Ganoë, C., & Mahar, J. (2009). wConnect: Cultivating a landscape of online places for a developmental learning community. *Educational Technology & Society*, 12 (4), 87-97.
- Rovai, A. (2002). Building a sense of community at a distance. *International Review of Research in Open and Distance Learning*, 3(1).
- Ruan, G., & Lin, Y. (2007). *An Online Peer Assisted Learning Community Model and its Application in ZJNU*. Paper presented at the International Educational Technology (IETC) Conference, 7th, Nicosia, Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus, May 3-5, 2007.
- Russell, M., & Ginsburg, L. (1999). *Learning Online: Extending the Meaning of Community. A Review of Three Programs from the Southeastern United States*. ERIC Document (ED437540)
- Schwier, R. A. (2007). Shaping the metaphor of community in online learning environments. In G. Calverley, M. Childs, & L. Schnieders (Eds.), *Videos for Education: Selected papers from the DIVERSE Conferences 2001-2006*, Volume 1, (pp. 68-76). Oxford, UK: Association for Learning Technology.
- Shannon, C. E., & Weaver, W. (1949). *The mathematical theory of communication*. Urbana, Illinois: University of Illinois Press.
- Shea, P., Swan, K., Li, C. S., & Pickett, A. (2005). Developing learning community in online asynchronous college courses: The role of teaching presence. *Journal of Asynchronous Learning Networks*, 9(4), 59-80.
- Short, J., Williams, E., & Christie, B. (1976). *The social psychology of telecommunications*. London: John Wiley.
- Slagter van Tryon, P.J., & Bishop, M.J. (2006). Identifying e-mmediacy strategies for web based instruction: A Delphi study. *Quarterly Review of Distance Education*, 7(1), 49-62.
- Snyder, Martha M. (2009). Instructional-Design Theory to Guide the Creation of Online Learning Communities for Adults. *TechTrends: Linking Research and Practice to Improve Learning*, 53(1), 48-56.
- Soylu, F. (2009). Designing online learning communities: Lessons from Eksisozluk. *European Journal of Open, Distance and E-Learning*, 2.
- Stepich, D. and Ertmer, P. (2003). Building community as a critical element of online course Design. *Educational Technology*, 43(5), 33-43.
- Stillings, N. A. (1995). Cognitive psychology: The architecture of the mind. In N. A. Stillings, & S. E. Weisler (Eds.), *Cognitive science* (pp. 15-86). Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press.

- Tsai, I.-C., Laffey, J. M., & Hanuscin, D. (2010). Effectiveness of an Online Community of Practice for Learning to Teach Elementary Science. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 43(2), 225-258.
- Tu, C. -H. (2002). The relationship between social presence and online privacy. *Internet and Higher Education*, 5, 293-318.
- Tu, C. -H., & McIsaac, M. (2002). The relationship of social presence and interaction in online classes. *The American Journal of Distance Education*, 16(3), 131-150.
- Velez, A. M. (2009). The ties that bind: How faculty learning communities connect online adjuncts to their virtual institutions. *Online Journal of Distance Learning Administration*, 12(2).
- Vonderwell, S., Liang, X., & Alderman, K. (2007). Asynchronous discussions and assessment in online learning. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 39(3), 309-328.
- Vratulis, V., & Dobson, T. M. (2008) Social negotiations in a wiki environment: a case study with pre-service teachers, *Educational Media International*, 45(4), 285-294.
- Vygotsky, L. (1978). *Mind and society*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Waddill, D. D. (2006). Action E-learning: An exploratory case study of action learning applied online. *Human Resource Development International*, 9(2) 157-171.
- Wang, Y. -M., & Chen, D. -T. (2010). Promoting spontaneous facilitation in online discussions: designing object and ground rules. *Educational Media International*. 47(3), 247-262.
- Wiener, M., & Mehrabian, A. (1968). *Language within language: Immediacy, a channel in verbal communication*. New York, NY: Appleton-Century-Crofts.
- Woods, R., & Keeler, J. (2001). The effect of instructor's use of audio e-mail messages on student participation in and perceptions of online learning: a preliminary case study. *Open Learning*, 16(3), 263-278.
- Yang, C.-C., Tsai, I.-C., Cho, M.-H., Kim, B., & Laffey, J. (2006). Exploring the relationships between students' academic motivation and social ability in online learning environments. *Internet and Higher Education*, 9(4), 277-286.
- Yeh, Y.-C. (2010). Integrating collaborative PBL with blended learning to explore preservice teacher' development of online learning communities. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 26, 1630-1640.
- Zydney, J. M., deNoyelles, A., & Seo, K. K.-J. (2012). Creating a community of inquiry in online environments: An exploratory study on the effect of a protocol on interactions within asynchronous discussions. *Computers & Education*, 58, 77-87.